

THE EFFECTS OF PROJECT-BASED LEARNING ON STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AND RETENTION IN METAL CORROSION IN SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ABAK LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA.

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Abstract: *The study investigated the effects of project-based learning on students' Academic Achievement and retention in Metal Corrosion in Senior Secondary schools in Abak Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The study adopted the pretest, posttest non-randomized quasi-experimental research design. The instrument used for data collection was Achievement Test on metal corrosion (ATMC) and reshuffled and used as retention test, with a reliability value of 0.79 using Kuder-Richardson Coefficient of reliability. The same test was reshuffled and used as retention test. The target population of the study was all the SS2 Chemistry students in the study area. A sample of 150 students comprising boys and girls drawn from three schools out of 12 schools in Abak Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria The sample was random sampling technique. Three research questions and three hypotheses were answered using mean and standard deviation scores. The hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance using analysis of covariance (ANCOVA). The moderate influence of gender was also observed. The findings indicated that students taught metal corrosion using learning by design model had significantly higher achievement mean scores than those taught using cyclic inquiry model. Students taught metal corrosion using coached ideation and experiential learning model. Findings showed no significant difference between the achievements mean scores of male and female students taught metal corrosion using the two project-based learning models. Based on the findings, it was recommended amongst others that Chemistry teachers should be trained on the impact and use of these models of learning, and implemented same during classroom instructions. The project-based learning model is not gender sensitive; therefore, both male and female students should be practically involved in assigned tasks using these models in order to enhance proper academic achievement and retention both in metal corrosion and other concepts in science.*

INTRODUCTION

Education is a process that nurtures human abilities, knowledge, skills and moral values. In

the broadest sense, it is a process by which an individual gains knowledge, insight and develops knowledge and skills necessary for

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proper functioning in the society. It is an experience that has a formative on the mind, character and physical abilities of individuals, a process by which society deliberately its accumulated knowledge, values, skills from one generation to another. It is of note that the overall development of any nation is inextricably tied to its education system. It is in realization of the fact, that the Nigerian national policy on education (NPE, 2018) asserts that “education is an instrument of social change”. Hence, some of the goals of education in Nigeria are the: development of the individual into a morally sound, patriotic and effective citizen. It also include total integration of the individual into the immediate community, the Nigerian and the world; and development of appropriate skills, mental, physical and social abilities and competencies to empower the individual to live and contribute positively to the society (NPE, 2018).

Education is a process by which the personality of a child is developed. Thus, the education of tomorrow should be able to play its role more effectively by making the individual creative, innovative and effective. Hence, some of the goals of education in Nigeria are the: development of the individual into a morally sound, patriotic and effective citizen; total integration of the individual into the immediate community, the Nigerian and the world; and development of appropriate skills, mental, physical and social abilities and competencies to empower the individual to live and contribute positively to the society. The educational system is growing and new innovations initiated

globally makes it imperative for education curriculum to be modified to meet present challenges (Kelly. 2018). Among those areas included in the education curriculum is science education, whose standards provide expectations for the development of understanding for students through science process skills.

Science education cultivates students’ curiosity about the world and enhances scientific thinking. Through the inquiry process, students will recognize the nature of science and develop scientific knowledge and science process skills to help them evaluate the impact of scientific and technological development. This will prepare students to participate in public discourse in science-related issues and enable them to become life-long learners. The emphasis of science education is to enhance students’ scientific literacy through investigative activities that involves planning, measuring, observing, analyzing data, designing and evaluating procedures and examining evidence. Learning science will enable learners to lead a fulfilling and responsible life by encouraging them to learn independently, deal with new situations, reason critically, think creatively, make informed decisions and solve problems through practical skills. Through science activities, students should develop an interest in science and thus they will be motivated to become active learners in science. Should be able to develop an understanding of the interrelationship between science, technology, society and environment and strengthen the ability to integrate and apply knowledge and skills across disciplines. They

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should be able to meet the changes and challenges in the ever-developing society and contribute immensely towards the scientific and technological world. Students with high ability or a strong interest in science needs more learning techniques which would stretch the students' science capabilities and offer opportunities for students to develop their potential to the fullest. Mkpa and Izuagba (2019) addressed the changing conception of the science education curriculum in reflecting new needs as problems emerge, students change in perception of a particular issue and make distinction on the role of schools. This definition may therefore, be used to evolve innovative skills and ideas which science teachers need to build upon to teach practical concepts.

Some science education subjects including mathematics physics, chemistry and biology education involves practical concepts which requires students' critical thinking to solve some scientific problems. Among these subjects is the chemistry education, where students' perception of difficult concepts affects their academic performance in examinations. One of the major goals in chemistry education is the development of basic practical skills which are critical in a highly technical, scientific as well as a complex modern society. Chemistry is central to every facet of life. It is the study of properties and composition of matter; its chemical reactions, structure and associated changes. It is primarily concerned with atoms and their interactions with other atoms, and particularly with the properties of chemical bonds. Chemistry is a science springing from the principles of physics

with its applications in other sciences such as life-sciences, engineering, technology, earth sciences and medicine (Suchocki, 2014; Davies, 2018 and Abanikannda, 2016). Chemistry graduates are engaged across the globe in rewarding careers in pharmaceutical, metallurgical firms, commercial laboratories, scientific research institutes, forensic scientists in the criminal justice system, universities, health services, food processing, petroleum and petro-chemical industry, biotechnology, toxicology, hazardous waste management, manufacturing industry, mining and extractive industry, medical technology, agriculture and forestry (Ababio, 2013; Helmenstine, 2019).

The interdisciplinary nature of chemistry also lends its graduates to collaborating with engineers, physicists and biologists in proffering solutions to a wide spectrum of societal problems. Chemistry is globally adjudged a prerequisite subject for the study of engineering, medicine, other basic and applied science courses in any tertiary institution. Oloruntegbe and Oduntuyi (2018) averred that a student who is deficient in chemistry, and has good grades in other science subjects will hardly be able to offer any course in the faculties of science, medicine and engineering in the universities. The ubiquity, pervasiveness, indispensability as well as vast career possibilities associated with chemistry notwithstanding, there is a palpable growing decline enrollment in Chemistry in Nigeria, particularly the private universities (Abanikannda, 2016). There are situations where only 4 students are enrolled and in other severe cases no enrollment at all. Several other

studies have further established and documented the phenomenon of low enrolment in chemistry in the Nigerian tertiary institutions (Kokotsaki., Menzies, Wiggins, (2016; Maduabum, 2005; Aina and Akanbi, 2013; Aderemi, Hassan, Siyanbola, and Taiwo, 2013; Osokoya, 2015). Glory (2020) alerted that chemistry was conspicuously missing from the list of 21 top sought after courses in Nigerian universities. Oloyede, and Ajimotokan, and Faruk, (2018), Nja, Cornelius-Ukpebi, Edoho and Neji (2020) noted consistent poor performance of secondary school students in Chemistry and attributed the cause to defective teaching pedagogy.

Chen (2013) observed that students' perception of Chemistry as a burden to be endured than as an experience to be valued results in phobia for Chemistry thereby impeding effective learning of the subject. Pengyue, *et al* (2020) hinted that a study in Malaysia revealed that many students perceived chemistry as too challenging, too abstract, boring and only tolerated because it is a compulsory subject for their preferred discipline. Other reasons identified for the dwindling interest and low level of performance in Chemistry include: insufficiency of qualified chemistry teachers, poorly equipped laboratories, poor study habits, lack of requisite infrastructure and poor funding (Gbore, 2006; Alam, Oloruntegbe and Orimogunje, 2010; Tafa, 2012). Akpan & Umanah (2024) revealed no significance difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students when taught gas laws using inquiry learning models. There is therefore the need to properly interrogate the

teaching and learning of Chemistry in schools with a view to discerning possible deficiencies and corrective mechanisms.

The study is predicated on the necessity of perpetuating and transferring the knowledge of Chemistry to the next generation. It is aimed at re-awakening interest and providing enabling environment for effective mastery of the subject. Chemistry as a discipline makes use of various modern teaching strategies to inculcate certain scientific skills and improve the quality of teaching in schools. These strategies help to develop students' interest and positive learning outcomes. Some of these strategies there are wide-range of design models that aims at enabling learning with real-world contexts such as: laboratory and workshops, apprenticeship, problem-based learning, case-based learning, project-based learning, enquiry-based learning, co-operative learning, field visit/industrial visit, expository learning, inquiry-based learning and computer-based etc.

Project-based learning with emphasis on this study involves choosing the idea, building a plan, executing the plan and finally evaluating it. When students pass through these stages, they can easily improve their skills to express ideas, solve problems, overcoming challenges, team work and self-assessment (Suchocki, 2014; Davies, 2018 and Abanikannda, 2016).. Project Based Learning is a teaching method in which students gain knowledge and skills by working for an extended period of time to investigate and respond to an authentic, engaging, and complex question, problem, or challenge. Project-based learning is a teaching strategy that focuses on

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real-world problems and challenges using problem-solving, decision-making and investigative skills. It is incredibly being used across disciplines because of its capacity to engage students in developing students in self-directed learning skills. Project-based learning is a student's centered methodology that engages students in developing critical thinking through undertaking authentic meaningful projects.

Project-based learning refers to an inquiry-based instructional method that engages learners in knowledge construction by having them accomplish meaningful projects and develop real-world products. Krajeik and Shin (2014) indicated six hallmarks of Project-based learning, including a driving question, the focus on learning goals, participation in educational activities, collaboration among students, the use of scaffolding technologies, and the creation of tangible artifacts. Among all these features the creation of artifacts that solve authentic problems is most crucial, which distinguishes Project-based learning from other student-centered pedagogies, for example, problem-based learning. This creation process requires learners to work together to find solutions to authentic problems in the process of knowledge integration, application, and construction. Instructors and community members (e.g. clients), normally as facilitators, provide feedback and support for learners to assist their learning process. Project-based learning courses frequently integrate a series of experiential-learning opportunities throughout the process (Suchocki, 2014; Davies, 2018 and Abanikannda, 2016). The purpose of these

experiences is to expand opportunities for students to discover, empathize, and understand the problem in different ways. In these activities, students are exposed to a direct "experience" related to the course topic or project question. This experience begins a process of reflection, discussion, analysis, and evaluation of the skills to guide further activities. Ideally, these experiences include exposure to circumstances, and people, not typically included in traditional classroom environments. Several review studies have predominantly focused on Project-based learning in post-secondary education. Helle, Tynjälä, and Olkinuora, (2006) discussed both the practice and impact of Project-based learning on students' learning. Regarding the practice, the authors found that most of the studies reviewed were confined to course descriptions in terms of course scope, instructor requirements, and team size. As for the impact, the review found that only a few studies investigated the influence of project-based learning on student learning related to either cognitive (e.g. knowledge) or affective outcomes (e.g. motivation). In another study, Ralph (2015) reviewed fourteen studies that adopted project-based learning in STEM education. It turned out that Project-based learning increased the development of both learners' knowledge and skills. Students also felt that project-based learning also encouraged their collaboration and negotiations within the group. However, some students reported a lack of motivation for teamwork. This is a strategy adopted in the teaching and learning which most teachers are not aware of. Several project-based

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learning strategies exist such as active-learning, inductive-learning, Backward Design, Experiential Activities, Haptic Engagement, Retrieval Practice, Metacognition & Problem-Solving Strategies, Just-in-Time Teaching, Guided Discovery, Coached Ideation, Visualizing Systems Thinking, Case-Study Method, Shared Solutions / Send-A-Problem, Learning Artifacts & Portfolios, Cooperative & Team-Based Learning, Role-Playing & Evaluation. For the purpose of this study, two of the project-based strategies outlined above would be considered, and they are: coached ideation and experiential activities.

Coached Ideation

At certain stages in the project-based learning/design thinking process, groups apply their knowledge of course content towards a project as they generate ideas. When the problems are complex, and the design process is collaborative, instructors must guide to facilitate these activities. A coached ideation process gives smaller groups of students a particular issue to address as it applies to the overall project (e.g., identifying options for non-conductive metals, prioritizing options for food distribution, etc.). The point isn't to solve the broader problem of project-based learning, but perhaps a crucial stage in one of the branch problems. These exercises should be short, somewhat informal, and ungraded interactions where students present ideas, explore, and evaluate collaboratively. Instructors should encourage all students to interact (modeling inclusive classroom tactics) and provide just-in-time learning to clear misconceptions, suggest case

studies, or provide technical expertise for concepts not apparent to student teams. The most important aspect of this process is that the work remains student-led. Doing so helps to emphasize student “voice and choice” while strengthening their engagement in the process. In a team-based learning process, this role of a “coach” may fall upon peer coaches or other team members.

Experiential Activities

Experiential learning is an educational approach that emphasizes personal or practical experience in the acquisition of knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes. Students are encouraged to develop a passion for learning and a thirst for knowledge by engaging in authentic experiences that allow them to learn what they need to know. Experiential learning requires the active engagement of the students as well as the instructor who serves as the facilitator of the learning process. It is intended to be an active, dynamic alternative to traditional classroom instruction that should be interactive and collaborative for those involved. Experiential learning activity is an application of knowledge and theory to real life experience. It fosters attainment of specific learning outcomes and encourages reflection and application of skills and knowledge and prepares students for a productive life outside the school environment. Experiential learning activities

- i. Integrates students with direct experiences and focuses on reflections and critical thinking.
- ii. Is constructed on previously existing knowledge and experiences

iii. Requires active involvement and participation in learning constructions

iv. Encourages, exchanges and collaborates ideas and perspectives.

v. Takes place mostly in classrooms and other learning environment.

The essential conditions that are required to ensure effective association of experiential learning activities in education are

vi. Activities that are supported by reflection, critical analysis and synthesis.

vii. Activities that require students' initiative, decision making skills and their accountability for results

viii. Students' participation in posing questions, investigations, experimentations, curiosity, problem solving skills, assuming responsibly, creativity and constructively.

Participation of students (physically, socially, emotionally and intellectually) is important for converting hands-on activity to minds-on activity. Most chemistry teachers find it difficult in transferring this knowledge about concepts such as corrosion of metals across to the students during classroom instructions. Hence, the need for this study.

Corrosion is one of the most common phenomena that we observe in our environment daily. You must have noticed that some objects made of iron are covered with an orange or reddish-brown coloured layer at some point in time. The formation of this layer is the result of a chemical process known as rusting, which is a form of corrosion. It is basically defined as a natural process that causes the transformation of pure metals into undesirable substances when

they react with substances like water or air. This reaction causes damage and disintegration of the metal, starting from the portion of the metal exposed to the environment and spreading to the entire bulk of the metal. Corrosion is usually an undesirable phenomenon since it negatively affects the desirable properties of the metal. For example, iron is known to have good tensile strength and rigidity (especially alloyed with a few other elements). However, when subjected to rusting, iron objects become brittle, flaky, and structurally unsound. On the other hand, corrosion is a diffusion-controlled process, and it mostly occurs on exposed surfaces. Therefore, in some cases, attempts are made to reduce the activity of the exposed surface and increase a material's corrosion resistance. Processes such as passivation and chromate conversion are used for this purpose. However, some corrosion mechanisms are not always visible, and they are even less predictable. On the other hand, corrosion can be classified as an electrochemical process since it usually involves redox reactions between the metal and certain atmospheric agents such as water, oxygen, Sulphur dioxide among others. Some factors affect the corrosion of metals include:

i. Exposure of the metals to air containing gases like CO_2 , SO_2 , SO_3 etc.

ii. Exposure of metals to moisture, especially salt water (which increases the rate of corrosion).

iii. Presence of impurities like salt (For example, NaCl).

iv. Temperature: An increase in temperature increases corrosion.

v. Nature of the first layer of oxide formed: Some oxides like Al_2O_3 form an insoluble protecting layer that can prevent further corrosion. Others, like rust, easily crumble and expose the rest of the metal.

vi. Presence of acid in the atmosphere: Acids can easily accelerate the process of corrosion. Some common examples of corrosion exist, and they are:

1. Copper Corrosion

When copper metal is exposed to the environment, it reacts with the oxygen in the atmosphere to form copper (I) oxide, which is red in colour.

Cu_2O further gets oxidised to form CuO , which is black in colour.

This CuO reacts with CO_2 , SO_3 and H_2O (present in the atmosphere) to form $\text{Cu}_2(\text{OH})_2(\text{s})$ (Malachite), which is blue in colour

and $\text{Cu}_4\text{SO}_4(\text{OH})_6(\text{s})$ (Brochantite), which is green in colour. This is why we observe copper turning bluish-green in colour. A typical example of this is the colour of the Statue of Liberty, which has the copper coating on it turning blue-green in colour.

2. Silver Tarnishing

Silver reacts with sulphur and sulphur compounds in the air, giving silver sulphide (Ag_2S), which is black in colour. Exposed silver forms Ag_2S as it reacts with the $\text{H}_2\text{S}_{(g)}$ in the atmosphere, which is present due to certain industrial processes.

3. Corrosion of Iron (Rusting)

Rusting of iron, which is the most commonly seen example, happens when iron comes in contact with air or water. The reaction could be seen as a typical electrochemical cell reaction. Consider the diagram given below.

Here, metal iron loses electrons and gets converted to $\text{Fe}_{\text{aq}}^{2+}$ (this could be considered as the anode position). The electrons lost will move to the other side, where they combine with H^+ ions. H^+ ions are released either by H_2O or by

H_2CO_3 present in the atmosphere (this could be considered as the cathode position).

The Hydrogen, thus formed by the reaction of H^+ and electrons, react with oxygen to form H_2O .

Anode reaction

Cathode reaction

Overall reaction

The Fe^{2+} ions formed at the anode react with oxygen in the atmosphere, thereby getting oxidized to Fe^{3+} and forming Fe_2O_3 , which comes out in the hydrated form as $Fe_2O_3 \cdot xH_2O$

For the purpose of this study, emphasis will be led on the rusting of iron.

Statement of problem

Project based learning have been recognized as one of the approaches which has helped to improve students' academic achievement in the past years. Although it has not been established that the current poor achievement in senior secondary school certificate examinations is as a result of improper utilization of the project-based learning strategy, the failure rate in science examinations is still alarming. As a result of this, many students find it difficult to cope with these educational challenges, and as such drop from sciences into arts. These difficulties may be due to students' inability to understand when taught using this strategy, chemistry teachers' ineffectiveness and non-utilization of project-based learning model and its application in the classrooms. This is also

applicable to the way metal corrosion is being taught. Sadly, this is hardly employed during instructions by teachers and this affects the understanding and learning outcomes of science concept like gas laws by students. Many students and teachers see metal corrosion as abstract and difficult to understand when encountered in Chemistry. Most teachers shy away from teaching the concept of metal corrosion as they appear complex and quite challenging to teach. These may result in students' poor achievement in both internal and external examinations.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of the study was to enhance the effect of project-based learning on students' academic achievement and retention in metal corrosion in senior secondary schools in Abak, Akwa Ibom State. Specifically, the study tends to:

1. To compare the differences in students' academic achievement mean score in chemistry when taught metal corrosion using coached-ideation and experiential activities?
2. Determine the academic achievement mean scores of male and female students in the concept of metal corrosion when taught using coached-ideation and experiential activities?
3. Determine the difference in students' interest scores on metal corrosion in chemistry when taught using coached-ideation and experiential activities?

Research Questions

1. What is the difference in students' academic achievement mean score in chemistry when taught metal corrosion using coached-ideation and experiential activities?

2. What is the difference in the academic achievement mean scores of male and female students in the concept of metal corrosion when taught using coached-ideation and experiential activities? What is the difference in students' interest scores on metal corrosion in chemistry when taught using coached-ideation and experiential activities?

Hypotheses Testing

The following null hypotheses guided the study

1. There is no significant difference in students' academic achievement mean score in chemistry when taught metal corrosion using coached-ideation and experiential activities?

2. There is no significant difference in the academic achievement mean scores of male and female students in the concept of metal corrosion when taught using coached-ideation and experiential activities?

3. There is no significant difference in students' interest scores metal corrosion in chemistry when taught using coached-ideation and experiential activities?

Methodology

For the purpose of this study, a quasi-experimental research design of pretest, posttest, experimental comparison groups (challenge-based model and inquiry-based model) was adopted. The population of this study comprised of 2,760 male and female senior secondary school students in Abak local government area, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria (state secondary Education students' enrollment board (2023/2024)). The target population of this study consist of 600 senior secondary school students. The sample size for this study was 150

male and female students in Abak, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Simple random sampling technique was employed for selection. The research instruments adopted for this study was a researcher-made Achievement Test on Metal corrosion (ATMC) which was later reshuffled and used for retention test, and used for data collection. The validation of instruments of the study was measured simultaneously with both face and content validity. The various comments and recommendations of the experts served as a guide for modification. Data analysis of the results obtained was carried out using descriptive statistics of mean, standard deviation and analysis of co-variance (ANCOVA), was used for analysis. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions while Analysis of Covariance was used to test the research hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance.

Presentation of Results

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation Scores of Students’ Pretest and Posttest Scores taught metal corrosion using coached-ideation and experiential activities?

Group	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Gain
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Coached Ideation	50	14.42	5.67	16.68	6.10	2.26
Experiential activities	50	12.70	3.72	16.84	5.73	1.14

Source: Descriptive Statistics of Data obtained

Results in Table1 show the mean gain score of the treatment groups; coached ideation and experiential activities as 2.26 and 1.14 respectively. This result indicates that students taught metal corrosion using experiential activities had the highest mean gain score,

followed by those taught using coached ideation who had the least mean gain score.

2 Research Question Two

What is the academic achievement mean scores of male and female students taught the concept of metal corrosion using coached ideation and experiential activities strategies?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation scores of male and female students’ pretest and posttest taught metal corrosion using coached ideation and experiential activities.

Model	Gender	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Gain
			Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Coached Ideation	Male	23	14.83	5.02	17.74	5.43	2.91
	Female	27	14.07	6.25	15.78	6.59	1.71
Experiential Activities	Male	23	12.43	3.15	16.26	18.74	3.83
	Female	27	12.93	4.20	14.48	15.22	1.55

Results in Table 2 show the mean gain of male students taught meatal corrosion using coached ideation and experiential activities strategy as 2.91, and 3.83 respectively, while those of their female counterparts are 1.71 and 1.55 respectively. This result indicates that male students’ mean gain score taught the concept of metal corrosion using coached ideation is higher

than that of their female counterparts while the male students’ mean gain score taught metal corrosion using experiential activities is higher than that of their female counterparts

Research Question Three

What differences exists in students’ retention scores on metal corrosion when taught using coached ideation and experiential activities?

Table 4.3: Mean and standard deviation scores of students’ posttest and retention taught metal corrosion using coached ideation and experiential activities.

Group	N	Posttest		Retention		Mean Gain
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Coached ideation	50	16.68	6.10	18.28	5.99	1.60
Experiential activities	50	16.84	5.73	17.52	6.24	0.68

Results in Table 3 shows the mean gain score of the treatment groups; coached ideation and experiential activities as 1.60 and 0.68 respectively. This result indicates that students taught metal corrosion using coached ideation had the highest mean gain score followed

by those taught using experiential activities who had the least mean gain score.

Hypotheses 1: There is no significant difference in students’ academic achievement mean score in chemistry when taught metal corrosion using coached-ideation and experiential activities

Table 4: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of the difference in students’ academic achievement mean score in chemistry when taught metal corrosion using coached-ideation and experiential activities.

Source of Variation		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig. at P<.05
Covariates	Pretest	1593.30	1	1593.30	575.61	0.00
Main Effects	Model	89.54	1	89.54	0.32	0.001
Residual		726.95	98	7.42		
Total		2409.79	100			

In Table 4, the calculated Probability value (P-value) .73 of the main effects (models) is less than the significance level (.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that at $P < .05$, there is a significant difference in the mean scores of students taught the concept of metal corrosion using coached ideation and experiential activities. This might be as a result of the several experiences gathered about the known concept of metal corrosion, as students were given opportunity to engage intellectually,

reflecting, posing questions and trying to arrive at solutions on metal corrosion. This finding is in line with who studied the effect of experiential learning activities on the attainment of specific learning outcome among senior secondary students in chemistry

Hypotheses 2: There is no significant difference in the academic achievement mean scores of male and female students in the concept of metal corrosion when taught using coached-ideation and experiential activities

Table 5: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of the difference in academic achievement mean scores of male and female students in the concept of metal corrosion when taught using coached-ideation and experiential activities

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision at p<.05 alpha
Corrected model	4162.217	1	4162.22	59.00	.000	S
Intercept	42.022	1	42.02	.60	.443	Ns
Pretest	8.235	1	8.24	.12	.734	Ns
Treatment * Gender	523.00	1	523.00	7.41	.659	s
Error	5290.65	96	70.54	-	-	-
Total	266849.00	100	-	-	-	-
Corrected Total	9997.88	99	-	-	-	-

R Squared = .470 (Adjusted R Squared = .456)

The result presented in Table 5 above revealed that the F-value of 7.41 of the main effects of gender obtained at 1 and 99 degrees of freedom had an associated p-value of 0.659, which is greater than 0.05 alpha level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is retained. This implies, there is no significant difference in the academic

achievement of male and female students taught the concept of metal corrosion using coached ideation and experiential activities

Hypotheses 3: There is no significant difference in students’ retention scores metal corrosion in chemistry when taught using coached-ideation and experiential activities

Table 6: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of the difference students’ retention scores on metal corrosion in chemistry when taught using coached-ideation and experiential activities

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision at p<.05 alpha
Pre-test (Covariate)	5643.40	1	5643.40	812.77	.000	S
Treatment	128.00	1	128.00	18.44	.000	S
Gender	.04	1	.04	.01	.939	Ns
Treatment *	442.98	1	442.98	63.82	.957	Ns
Error	520.76	46	6.94	-	-	-
Total	218279.00	50	-	-	-	-
Corrected Total	6819.387	49	-	-	-	-

R Squared = .924 (Adjusted R Squared = .920)

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The result presented in Table 6 above revealed that the F-value of 63.82 obtained at 1 and 49 degrees of freedom had an associated p-value of 0.957, which is greater than 0.05 alpha level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is retained. This implies that at $P < .05$, there no significant difference in the students' retention scores on metal corrosion when taught using coached ideation and experiential activities

Discussion of findings

In Table 4, the first finding revealed that the calculated Probability value (P-value) .73 of the main effects (models) is less than the significance level (.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that at $P < .05$, there is a significant difference in the mean scores of students taught the concept of metal corrosion using coached ideation and experiential activities. This finding is in line with Pan, Seow, Shankararaman and Koh, (2020) whose major findings confirmed that experiential learning is more effective for enhancing the scientific achievement and Interest of students in the subject of science. The research has applications for in-service or pre-service teachers, parents, policymakers of curriculum framework and students at schools. Data were treated by Mean, SD and t-test. The findings of the study reveal that the experiential learning method plays an important role in enhancing achievement in science in comparison to traditional teaching methods

In table 5, the second finding revealed the calculated Probability value (P-value) .659 of the main effects of Gender is greater than the significance level (.05). Therefore, the null

hypothesis is retained. This implies that at $P < .05$, there is no significant difference in the academic achievement of male and female students taught the concept of metal corrosion using coached ideation and experiential activities. This finding is in line with Arokoyo (2020) which showed that experiential learning approach increased the performance of Chemistry students more than the conventional approach; it also showed that male students performed better than their female counterparts when taught with experiential learning approach.

In Table 6, the calculated Probability value (P-value) .24 of the main effects (models) is greater than the significance level (.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis is retained. This implies that at $P < .05$, there no significant difference in the students' retention scores on

Metal corrosion when taught using coached ideation and experiential activities. This finding is in line with Ajayi (2017) who revealed that students taught stoichiometry using hands-on activities had significantly higher mean achievement scores than those taught using demonstration method $F=555.374$, $P(0.0001 < 0.05)$ and students taught stoichiometry using hands-on activities had significantly higher mean retention scores than those taught using demonstration method $F=117.523$, $P(0.0001 < 0.05)$. There was no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught stoichiometry using hands-on activities

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were drawn: experiential activities had an enormous relationship with coached ideation strategy when adopted in the teaching and learning of metal corrosion in chemistry. It is recommended that the federal government

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should partner with the curriculum planners and other educational organization such as the Science Teachers Association of Nigeria to implement these strategies into Nigeria's educational system and provide trainings and professional awareness for teachers in order to enhance effective learning outcomes.

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